

Relationship between Academic Achievements and Teaching in Thailand

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Abstract:- Problem-solving Critical thinking, creativity Able to research the subjects that interest them appropriately Until becoming a sustainable knowledge and skill in the future, it is considered to modify one's teaching methods to be effective and consistent with the times. By prioritizing the learners, the students must be allowed to think for themselves. And consider the content to be most suitable for the learners. The instructor will be the only provider of the learning experience. And to facilitate, direct, follow up, and supervise to lead to the development of various skills to their full potential. development of both academic achievement and the ability to solve problems through heuristics that will help learners find answers to problems through their ability to link previous knowledge that has been learned or related concepts systematically by finding the relationship between the information you want to learn or the problem you want to solve. Let students know the root cause of the problem. Subproblems can be created from found problems to simplify them. Therefore, the researcher is to study the ability to solve problems in 4 areas: problem determination, and Analyzing the cause of the problem. problem-solving in terms of examination, affects learning achievement, affects the choice of teaching and learning management with a Heuristics thinking process. The results of the research showed that The results of the test correlation between problem-solving ability (X_1) and learning achievement. and the consideration of instructional management (Y) of private university students in Bangkok Overall, it was found that The relationship between the ability to solve problems (X_1) has a P-value equal to 0.000, less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.01$), that is, reject the main hypothesis H_0 , accept the secondary hypothesis H_1 , meaning that the ability to solve the problem (X_1) has Correlation with the relationship between academic achievement and considering the teaching and learning management (Y) of private university students in Bangkok area which can be written in the form of regression analysis as follows: $Y=1.102 + 0.744 (X_1)$

Keywords:- Academic, Achievements, Teaching, Heuristics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world today is a rapidly changing world. Human perception of information around the world is also happening rapidly. advances in science and technology making the vast world a world without borders of learning. Affecting the daily life of human beings in every aspect, such as work, and education, these things are considered to follow the process of invention and development of technology of others. To strengthen the immunity in the country Must focus on the development of people or human capital to be strong and able to learn. and develop themselves naturally to their full potential. Which focuses on promoting educational opportunities for the public in line with the needs of the country and strengthening competitiveness and cooperation with other countries by providing opportunities for everyone to have access to the education system thoroughly.

Thai people must be developed to become complete Thai people with discipline, attitudes, and behavior according to good social norms. Have citizenship Have the ability to adapt wisely to the situation Be responsible and contribute to the public Have good physical and mental health There is spiritual growth. Have a self-sufficient way of life and are Thai. The students will receive both knowledge. have been developing process and moral skills as specified by the Basic Education Core Curriculum 2008, especially the development of thinking skills in problem-solving by practicing solving a variety of problems and in a generally accepted direction.

Fig 1. Herbert A. Simon, a Nobel Laureate, and American economist, proposed the concept in the 1950s. (<https://www.wallstreetmojo.com/>)

Heuristics refers to a problem-solving and decision-making approach where individuals or entities consider past results or experiences and the minimal relevant details to reach a practical conclusion. These strategies utilize mental shortcuts and generalized concepts to find immediate, efficient, and short-term solutions. A heuristic model acts as a rule of thumb in cases where there is no time for careful consideration of different aspects of a situation. Though this technique does not always give accurate, rational, or optimal results, it satisfies the requirements awaiting valid conclusions or decisions in complex scenarios. Its purpose is to solve a problem or achieve an outcome quickly with minimal mental effort and without analyzing everything thoroughly. *How Does Heuristics Work?* Heuristics are problem-solving techniques to achieve a satisfactory solution using mental shortcuts based on previous outcomes with a similar situation. These are short-term results, letting individuals or entities tackle the issues for the time being. It, thus, gives them enough time to look at it in detail later on.

Herbert A. Simon, a Nobel Laureate, and American economist, proposed the concept in the 1950s. He claimed that humans try to make rational decisions but are ultimately impacted by cognitive heuristics. However, the technique gained traction following Israeli psychologist Daniel Kahneman's book "Thinking, Fast, and Slow." He hypothesized that these biases have an impact on how people think and make decisions.

Heuristics may be the most effective method for resolving problems, whether they are personal or professional. These short-term results provide ample time to make decisions that will solve difficulties permanently. The strategy has been found effective, if not accurate, as a short-term technique for dealing with problems or making correct decisions. Nevertheless, it has also been regarded as a method of reducing effort. Many theories call it an approach indicative of cognitive laziness. Those who do not want to put much mental effort opt for this method for making judgments or solving problems. For some psychologists, the technique can cause cognitive biases. The findings or choices reached in previous cases based on cognitive abilities become the basis for conclusions or decisions for others with better-thinking levels.

The heuristics definition has become more prominent with the advent of technology, making all types of data available online. People can research, examine, and evaluate data from multiple sources to reach conclusions and make quick and efficient decisions. *Importance Of Heuristics* Heuristics is infamous for producing cognitive biases due to data limitations, which cause people and corporations to make poor decisions. Understanding the notion is therefore critical to avoid such a predicament and participate in more adaptive activities. It is worth noting that mental shortcuts, i.e., readily and widely available information, aid in making quick decisions in difficult circumstances or finding appropriate solutions to complex problems with limited time and resources. *Types Of Heuristics Methods* Here are the various sorts of heuristics based on the sources, contexts, and problems from which one derives the solutions or decisions:

Fig 2. Types Of Heuristics Methods
(<https://www.wallstreetmojo.com/>)

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The researcher is interested in studying

- To study general information of students such as gender, age, year of study and faculty affect academic achievement
- To study the ability to solve 4 problems, i.e., problem determination, and Analyze the cause of the problem. problem-solving in terms of examination, affects learning achievement, affects the choice of teaching and learning management with the Heuristics thinking process
- To use the information for the benefit of teaching and learning for academic achievement study and consideration of teaching and learning management for students' private universities.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data collection was collected data from private university students in Bangkok. The 515 people were randomly sampled in the descriptive statistics section. The statistics used to test the hypothesis were multiple regression analyses.

IV. RESULTS

The results of the research showed a correlation between problem-solving ability and learning achievement. and the consideration of instructional management of private university students in Bangkok Overall, it was found that The relationship between the ability to solve problems has a P-value equal to 0.000, less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.01$), that is, reject the main hypothesis H_0 , accept the secondary hypothesis H_1 , meaning that the ability to solve the problem has Correlation with the relationship between academic achievement and considering the teaching and learning management of private university students in Bangkok area which can be written in the form of regression analysis is as follows:

$$Y=1.102 + 0.744 (X_1)$$

Table 1. Stepwise multiple regression analysis

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P value
Regression	78.000	1	78.000	539.068	0.000
Residual	53.332	369	0.145		
Total	131.333	370			

Multiple R 0.770
R Square 0.594
Adjusted R Square 0.588
Standard Error 0.380

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results were discovered in this study.

- Consideration of Teaching and Learning Management of Private University Students in the Bangkok Area for Academic achievement guidelines for developing has a way of developing the towards learning, in the four components as follows::
 - Analysis of the cause of the problem In terms of analyzing and defining the details of the problem, one must know what the requirements are. What information is provided? Consider whether or not the information and conditions given are enough to find the answer to the problem. If this is not enough, more information should be sought.
 - problem-solving in planning to solve problems when understanding should plan to solve problems by choosing tools and how to get answers Experience will be used at this stage. "Have you ever solved a problem like this?" in case of previous experience. Experience should be used as a guideline for solving problems by improving them to suit new problems.
 - In terms of inspection and improvement, after step 3 has been performed, the results will be taken to check whether the problem has been solved or not. If solved, it is considered successful. But if it can't be solved There must be a way to improve.
 - Troubleshooting operations when planning therefore proceeding to solve problems and to design teaching and learning.

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Correlation between problem-solving ability and learning achievement and the consideration of instructional management of private university students in Bangkok Overall, it was found that The relationship between the ability to solve accept the secondary hypothesis H₁, meaning that the ability to solve the problem has a Correlation with the relationship between academic achievement and considering the teaching and learning management of private university students in Bangkok area.

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